

Fablabs and SDGs: from Awareness via Alignment to Accountability and Impact-by-Design

Pieter van der Hijden, Nagwa Elnwisy, Vaneza Caycho

*Pieter van der Hijden, Sofos Consultancy,
Amsterdam, The Netherlands,
pvdh@sofos.nl*

*Nagwa Elnwisy, Researcher and Lecturer at Suez Canal University,
Ismailia, Egypt,
nagwa.elnwisy@gmail.com*

*Vaneza Caycho, Universidad Nacional Federico Villarreal,
Lima, Peru,
2018036914@unfv.edu.pe*

Abstract

This paper reviews the maturation process that the Global Working Group “Fablabs and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)” has gone through and in which they tried to involve more and more fablabs in the SDGs.

During the FAB13 Conference in Chile (2017) "Fabricating Society" the former Fablab Life Cycle Working Group transformed into a new Fablabs & UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Working Group. At first this WG mainly aimed for Awareness from the fablabs about the SDGs. The next stage was that of Alignment. The WG asked the fablabs to determine an SDG profile and to align their internal policy with it. More than 21% of the fablabs have now done this. The working group provides monthly overviews and statistics.

The next challenge is actually helping to realize social impact as expressed in the SDG sub-goals ("targets"). The WG will present how it is working on this (including with a management game) and discuss the merits of this approach.

The process this group has gone through can be expanded or generalized as a model for effective fablab involvement in SDGs implementation.

Keywords

Fablab, fablabs, fablab network, awareness, alignment, action, accountability, impact, impact-by-design, maturity level, sdg, sdgs

Figure 1: Impression of a fablab (Courtesy: Fablab Vestmannaeyjar, Iceland)

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1.1 Fablabs

Fablabs are open workshops for digital fabricating. Visitors, from young to old, can receive training, but above all they can also get to work themselves with the digital machines and computers with dedicated software. Neil Gershenfeld of the MIT Center for Bits and Atoms developed the concept around 2005 (Gershenfeld, N et al. 2017). In 2010 there were already 50 fablabs, in 2024 there will be 2500 worldwide. Fablabs can be embedded in an educational institution, a community center or a company, but also stand alone. In principle, they are autonomous organizations that work together as a Fablab network, supported by the Fab Foundation led by Sherry Lassiter (Portal: Fab Foundation). That foundation organizes a number of global course programs, including the Fab Academy, an annual international conference and more.

1.2 SDGs

In 2015, a globally organized bottom-up process of the United Nations culminated in resolution A/RES/70/1 in its General Assembly entitled “Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development”. In short: the 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). All 193 UN member states agreed to this.

The goals do not only apply to developing countries, but to all countries. They have been elaborated into 169 targets that indicate the concrete impact to be achieved. The whole forms a broad socio-economic program for all countries in the world. Combating climate change and its impact is part of this (strictly speaking, this falls under the UNFCCC). Leave No One Behind is the central motto. The source documents have been translated into many languages; the associated logos too.

The governments of the 193 member states implement these 17 goals and 169 underlying targets and report on them periodically on a voluntary basis. The United Nations facilitate, including by setting up and agreeing on a system of indicators (now 242+). The United Nations Development Program (UNDP) particularly supports developing countries in this process, a.o. by setting-up so-called Accelerator Labs (Portal: UNDP Accelerator Labs).

Figure 2: Registered Fablabs with linear and exponential trend lines; medio 2010 (Zijlstra, 2010), ultimo 2011-2013 (Portal: Labs), ultimo 2019 – medio 2024 (Portal: Fablabs.io)

Implementing "the goals" would cost trillions of dollars annually. Amounts that cannot be raised from public funds. It is therefore important to mobilize the entire society and see the goals as the global socio-economic program for the entire world to which every city, every organization and every individual contributes. This includes every fablab and the fablab network.

1.3 Working group

The Global Working Group Fablabs and the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) emerged from the previous Fablab Life Cycle Working Group (Portal: Fablabs and SDGs). At the fablab conference in New Zealand (2012), the Fab Foundation asked four participants to set up an ad hoc workshop on Fablab Life Cycle: How to Start your own Fablab, Sustainability, Advocacy and Marketing, and Fab Courses to Help. That happened, caught on and the working group was born.

The working group then developed an improved version of the workshop given at the Fablab conferences in Spain (2014), USA (2015) and China (2016). In the meantime, all experiences were bundled in a publication "The Fablab Life Cycle; Report of the FAB10 workshops" (Van der Hijden & Juarez, 2012).

After China, the working group thought it was time for the next level: the orientation of fablabs on society. Resolution A/RES/70/1 "Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development" (United Nations, 2015) adopted by all UN member states seemed to be a good unifying element for fablabs in all countries.

2 Maturity levels

In 2017, the working group changed its name to the Global Working Group on Fablabs and UN Sustainable Development Goals. At that time, the SDG program was still relatively new. Many countries had also not yet anchored it in their policy cycles. The problem was also new for the working group itself, let alone for the fablabs that we wanted to involve. The goals themselves were appealing, but what should be the path to achieving them?

Figure 3: Poster with the 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations)

Initially, the WG mainly focused on making the fablabs aware of the SDGs. The group learned from this that more focus was needed to actually take action: Alignment. The WG asked the fablabs to focus on 2-4 SDGs (their "SDG Profile") and align their activities accordingly. Up until now (medio 2024), 512 out of 2472 fablabs (21%) have done this. The working group provides monthly overviews and statistics (WG Fablabs & SDGs, 2018...).

After Awareness and Alignment, the WG saw more and more SDG-related Actions emerge in the fablab network. Partly traceable to the previous Alignment, partly autonomous. The WG monitors and tries to connect people and offer support where possible.

The WG believes that all these well-intentioned actions are useful, but still have little demonstrable impact. It sees the next challenge as actually helping to realize the social impact as expressed in the SDG sub-goals ("targets"), to commit to this and to be accountable. This Accountability is still under development, both for the WG and for the fablab network.

The WG now recognises Awareness, Alignment, Action and Accountability as four stages of maturity. However, each fablab makes its own autonomous choices and considerations. They decide for themselves whether they want to "mature" and at what pace. So we can expect to find fablabs at all levels of maturity. This means that a WG (of volunteers) that mainly promotes, encourages and facilitates will have to continue to pay attention to all these different levels.

Figure 4: Maturity Levels (Global WG Fablabs & SDGs)

The image above provides an example of the four SDG maturity levels. On the far left is Pre-Awareness. To the right we successively pass through Awareness (with a global view of all SDGs), via Alignment (with a focus on a limited number of SDGs) to Action (concrete activities related to one of the goals) to Accountability (commitment to one of the targets).

2.1 Awareness

During the FAB conference in Chile (2017), the working group organized a "Workshop Sustainable Fablab Goals". The most important lessons from this Spanish/English workshop were:

- The local participants highly appreciated that the workshop was bilingual (handouts in two languages, a facilitator for the local language); the working group has continued to do so ever since;
- The fablabs and conditions worldwide are too diverse to agree on one common focus within the SDGs;
- For the future, it seemed better to let each fablab determine its own focus, for example by each determining a selection from the SDGs that best suited that fablab; the fablabs could share that "profile" among themselves and with the outside world and seek cooperation on that basis.

Later at the same FAB conference, the SDG approach received explicit support from Neil Gershenfeld. He and his brothers gave an advance on the publication "Designing Reality" (Gershenfeld, N. et al., 2017) that the three of them had written. They highlighted how at several international meetings it became clear that access to digital manufacturing was simply required to implement the SDGs (p.53). And conversely, they approvingly quoted Ton Kalil, former deputy director of the White House Office of Science and Technology Policy, that the fablab's progress will be measured by the extent to which it can solve specific social problems. Self-expression alone is not enough (p.92).

It was clear to the working group that the SDGs were a useful vehicle for increasing the social significance of fablabs. The applied method however should do justice to the wide variety of fablabs and the contexts in which they operated. The working group wanted to ask each fablab for an SDG profile, i.e. a selection of 2-4 SDGs that best suit that fablab. They could then align their own organization with this and pursue cooperation with other fablabs on that basis.

According to the working group, all this would help to 1) strengthen the global fab community 2) without sacrificing the autonomy and uniqueness of each fablab. For the outside world the fablab network could become a more coherent organization, with a presence on the ground in many countries, innovative and not profit driven and loved by young people. In other words: 3) an ideal partner to include in consortia for SDG programs.

Figure 5: SDG-09 and its targets; awareness includes the realization that the 17 SDGs each have a number of underlying "targets" that are much more concrete than the goals

2.2 Alignment

During the FAB conference in France (2018), the working group organized a completely new workshop "Fablabs and Sustainable Development Goals".

This workshop focused on Awareness and Alignment. The first was a brief introduction to the SDGs, the second was drawing up an SDG profile for their own fablab (the 2-4 SDGs that suited them best) and then a reflection on adjusting the local activity plans in the direction of that profile and on collaboration with other fablabs based on SDG profiles (Repository: SDG Workshop) (Van der Hijden, P., Caycho V. et al., 2018).

Figure 6: Impression of the SDG Alignment workshop during FAB14, Toulouse, France, 2018

The most important lessons from this French/English workshop were:

- Although the workshop format was actually intended for a group of participants from one and the same fablab, the 24 workshop participants from 19 countries handled it effortlessly. It ultimately led to an initial collection of 16 Fablab SDG profiles.
- The workshop format turned out to be useful, but to make such workshops possible for large numbers of fablabs, a good manual for fablab managers would be needed. This was subsequently created: "How to align your Fablab / Makerspace with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)" (Van der Hijden, Caycho et al. 2018). This allows fablab managers to organize an Alignment workshop locally with their management, staff and volunteers.
- The workshop participants are drowning in papers (see picture above). To prevent this (chaos, environment, costs, organization), the working group has also made online documentation available about the SDGs (Tool, 2018).
- The fablabs would like to submit their SDG profile and see it in joint overviews. The working group started managing and publishing this data, including in an online interactive mindmap with monthly updates (WG Fablabs & SDGs, 2018 ...).

Figure 7: Planning board (A3 form) (fictional data)

SDG Planning Board		EXAMPLE		
FAB LAB XXX		<p>Identify new opportunities for the fab lab network</p>		
<p>4 QUALITY EDUCATION</p> <p>4. Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all</p>	<p>Many activities in this field: information and demonstration to general public at events, workshops for different age groups, courses for 2D design and laser cutting, 3D design and 3D printing, fab academy, etc.</p>	<p>NEW on our agenda: X Adults with almost no education, bring them back to learning processes, empower them for new job opportunities</p>	<p>Documenting our education activities and materials and actively offering them to our neighbour fab labs.</p>	
<p>8 DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH</p> <p>8. Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work for all</p>	<p>Two staff members with expertise in organizational health and safety, not only important internally, but we include it in many projects as well.</p>	<p>NEW on our agenda: X develop a practical toolkit for safety ambassadors</p>	<p>Searching other fab labs interested in decent work and trying to create a handbook on that topic together.</p>	
<p>9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE</p> <p>9. Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization, and foster innovation</p>	<p>Especially young professionals and technopreneurs: all is about new products and services, especially software and connectivity is very popular in our lab</p>	<p>NEW on our agenda: X Build LoraWAN in our place and use it for citizen sensing</p>	<p>Replicating software projects from CBA and see how we could apply them locally</p>	
<p>17 PARTNERSHIPS FOR THE GOALS</p> <p>17. Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalise the global partnership for sustainable development</p>	<p>Partnerships with local organizations, especially the support chain for new startups, active member of fab region and global network.</p>	<p>NEW on our agenda: X active contribution to fab region network X finally run our own fab academy</p>	<p>Looking for our sister fab labs, communicating with them and planning at least one common activity this year</p>	

Figure 8: Excerpt from monthly overview of Fablab SDG Profiles

2.3 Action

The working group assumed that the fablabs themselves would look for collaboration with other fablabs. They thus reached a new stage: Action. The working group anticipated that specific support would again be welcome, for example in preparing SDG tenders, organizing projects and professionalizing the fablab staff. However, the working group's capabilities are limited. It is a group of volunteers, each with their own commitments. The intervention options are mainly offering activities at fablab conferences, arranging publications and sending mailings. With all three of these types it is important to do this in moderation.

Figure 9: Various actions within the fablab network

The image above shows what is going on within the fablab regarding the SDGs. Regional partnerships are paying attention to this, some fablabs are already taking sectoral initiatives, e.g. Fab Care, a recurring theme is also the Humanitarian issues, and of course the SDGs also apply in-house (e.g. safety). Finally, other organizations also call on us.

The working group was looking for what could be a useful contribution in this multifaceted phase. Here we briefly indicate the activities and most important lessons.

- 2019: During the FAB conference in Egypt (2019), the working group gave an Arabic/English/Spanish workshop "Fablabs & SDGs: the next round". The participants worked in groups on assignments in the areas of A. Enhance our SDG experience; B. Start working with MDBs (Multilateral Development Banks).
Lessons learned: from now on, offer beginners and advanced participants separate workshops.
- 2020: Due to the pandemic, the next FAB conference (2020) was online. The working group offered two workshops: for beginners the Alignment workshop, for advanced participants "Experience the world of SDG projects in our management game". In the latter the government formulates a Request-for-Proposals, a fablab comes up with a proposal and an MDB (Multilateral Development Bank) with an assessment thereof.
Lessons learned: given the limitations (online group work), everything worked out quite well, game approach with role change was positive; content should be more about the project content and less about the formal procedures.
- 2021: The FAB conference in Canada (2021) also took place largely online. The working group offered two workshops. The SDG Alignment workshop again for beginners. For advanced participants "Fabricate our commons with the SDGs", consisting of group discussions on:
 - Prepare for future disasters: resilience is the keyword
 - Become commercially viable AND integrate the Base-of-Pyramid
 - Start networking with your sister labs
 - Move to social impact

Lessons learned: The format used was suitable for quickly gauging interests and views on multiple topics. One by one, the chosen topics turned out to be candidates for follow-up workshops.

- 2022: The FAB conference in Indonesia (2022) was physical again. The working group was given a 4-hour time slot for workshops. We then held four one-hour workshops that built on each other. Participants could decide for themselves which parts they wanted to follow. It was about:
 1. Awareness and Alignment
 2. Action: Designing SDG based learning activities for your fablab
 3. Action: Involving your fablab in SDG tenders for public projects
 4. Action: Developing the implementation plan for your fablab project

Lessons learned: The construction of successive workshops for partly different target groups was well received. The coherence between the components was strengthened by using the output of one workshop as input for the next. Yet it remained floating above the market that impact is what matters. This is actually quite vague. Isn't it time to take the bull by the horns: impact by design?

2.4 Accountability

Alignment familiarizes organizations with the SDGs and allows them to slightly adapt their current activities to their preferred SDGs, their so-called SDG profile.

At Actions, one or more fablabs respond to questions from the outside world, as expressed in a tender procedure, or they themselves define manageable goals and work on them .

But what is the real effect of all those actions? Do they have a social impact and how do you demonstrate that? Many projects make it plausible that their output (e.g. training) will eventually lead to the intended impact (e.g. reduction in youth unemployment), but does that really happen?

In the view of the WG, accountability means that fablabs commit to achieving a well-defined impact and are also accountable for this. Impact is not a self-devised statement, but a concrete SDG target that is achieved within a specific context, e.g. a city.

Figure 10: From Inputs to Impact (Rogers, 2014)

Inputs	The financial, human and material resources used in a programme or policy. For example, training materials produced.
Outputs	The immediate effects of programme/policy activities, or the direct products or deliverables of programme/policy activities. For example, the number of vaccines administered.
Outcomes	The likely or achieved short-term and medium-term effects of a programme or policy's outputs, such as a change in vaccination levels or key behaviours.
Impact	Positive and negative, primary and secondary long-term effects produced by a development intervention, directly or indirectly, intended or unintended. (OECD-DAC definition, 2010)

Too often, the working group sees that projects "justify" their impact by arriving at the desired impact from the outcomes via a plausible scenario. The working group sees more merit in the opposite path. This starts with formulating the desired impact (impact-by-design) and then reasoning back to the actions to

be taken to achieve this. A fablab then makes a commitment (probably together with partners) for the impact to be achieved and can be held accountable for it.

- 2023: During the FAB conference in Bhutan (2023), the working group delivered the workshop "From SDG Alignment to SDG Impact". It is a management game in which the participants alternate playing roles: 1. policy maker in the government, 2. manager of an SDG development fund and 3. Fablab manager. The game is a frame game and can be "loaded" with a case of your choice. In the case of Bhutan, this was the data from the Sustainable Development Report 2023 for Bhutan and the current data on Fablab SDG profiles in Bhutan. Lessons learned: 1. it is important that at least three groups of three players participate; 2. a playing time of two hours is not enough, preferably 3-4 hours so that there is more opportunity for mutual exchange and feedback.
- 2024: An improved version "From SDG Alignment to SDG Impact" is scheduled for the conference in Mexico (August 2024); the case is Mexico 2024; the session lasts 4 hours.

3 Results

The activities of the working group consist of workshop formats / management games and holding sessions thereof, semi-annual mailings to all fablabs to call for the preparation of SDG profiles and/or keeping their registration up to date on fablabs.io, processing the Fablab SDG Profiles and publishing an monthly overview of all Fablab SDG Profiles (WG Fablabs & SDGs, 2018 ...).

The most important quantitative result are the SDG profiles from which all kinds of other information can be derived. Here we provide a small anthology of the results.

3.1 Fablab SDG Profiles

Fablabs that submit their SDG profile will receive confirmation by email within a week. The working group adds the received profile to an online interactive mindmap with a global overview of all Fablab SDG Profiles. This was initially done manually, but it eventually became too laborious.

It was less laborious to develop a simple programming language for mindmaps and an interpreter to process scripts in that language (Van der Hijden, P. 2022). This allowed the SDG profiles to be linked to the fablab register on fablabs.io and to all kinds of external data collections such as the Sustainable Development Report (Sachs, J.D. et al., 2024) and the websites of Natural Earth (geospatial data), GeoNames (per country the area, population and flag) and Wikipedia (especially ISO3166 country list). The data is read and edited via Jupyter Notebook, resulting in a script for the mindmap and about a hundred graphs that are linked via an external website (Repository: Fablab Network Data).

Figure 11: Fablab SDG Profiles (timeline)

As a percentage of the number of fablabs, the percentage has been fluctuating around 20% for several years. Fablabs could submit their SDG profile online. This has happened 624 times to date and includes both new submissions and updates. The net number of operational fablabs with a Fablab SDG profile is 512 (medio 2024).

3.2 SDG frequencies

Figure 12: World: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

World: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):

World: fablabs: 2,472; fablab sdg profiles: N = 512 (= 21 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01

Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)

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The graph above indicates the frequency with which the 17 SDGs appear in the Fablab SDG profiles (worldwide). The outliers are SDG04 Quality Education and SDG09 Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure. It is also striking that the SDGs in the areas of poverty, hunger, clean water, reduced inequalities, climate action, life below water (ocean), life on land (forest) and peace score very low.

The WG publishes these figures also per continent and even per country in its monthly online overview (Overview of Fablab SDG Profiles). It turns out that in most continents, SDG04 and SDG09 remain the outliers, but in Europe SDG09, SDG11 and SDG12 "compete" for second place. The low scores at a global level are also reflected in the individual continents. Africa and South America score 0% when it comes to SDG16 (Peace); South America same for SDG02 (Zero Hunger).

3.3 Fablab information

The WG publishes selected information on fablabs with SDG profiles. As an example we take Fablab Puebla from Mexico. The Fablab Puebla info card states, among other things, the number of Global SDG Profile Peers. That is, the number of fablabs worldwide that have exactly the same SDG profile as Fablab Puebla. In this case there are five (Fablab Puebla included). Via the overview of all Fablab SDG Profiles the peers can be filtered. The figure below shows the result.

Figure 13: Fablab SDG Profiles SDG-04-08-09-10 peers

3.4 Country information

The working group has information available on almost every country in the world; most of course about the countries with Fablab SDG Profiles. As an example, we look at the information we have about Mexico. We show an Info Card with some statistical data, a graph with SDG profile frequencies and the country profile from The Sustainable Development Report 2024 (Sachs et al. 2024).

Figure 14: Info Card Mexico

Mexico
✕

Entity: Country ✕

Sovereignty: UN member ✕

Language: Spanish ✕

Population Size: 100-1,000 million ✕

Fablab Density: 0 criteria met ✕

Continent	North America
Capital city	Mexico City
Area [10,000 km ²]	197.25
Population [mil]	126.19
Fablabs	50
Fablabs with SDG Profile	18 (= 36 %)
Fabcity members	4
Fablabs / 10,000 km ² Area	0.25 (<1 = criterion not met)
Fablabs / mil Population	0.40 (<1 = criterion not met)
Fablab Density	0 criteria met
2024 SDG Index Score	69.3%

Mexico Fablabs on fablabs.io

Mexico Fablab SDG Profiles (Frequencies)

Mexico Country SDG Dashboard 2024

The information card of Mexico contains some statistical data about the country and the fablabs. It can be seen that there are 50 fablabs, of which 18 (= 36%) have drawn up a Fablab SDG Profile. That percentage is high, worldwide it is 21%. Yet the number of fablabs is not high enough to meet one, let alone two, of the fablab density criteria.

Figure 15: Mexico: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG Frequencies [%]

The bar graph shows the frequencies from the Fablab SDG Profiles of Mexico. Deviating from the global picture and from the picture for North America, SDG04 (Quality Education) in Mexico is not first, but only third. First is SDG09 (Industry, innovation and infrastructure), second is SDG08 (Decent work and economic growth). SDG02 (zero hunger), SDG14 (life below water) and SDG15 (life on land) score 0%.

Finally, the country profile for Mexico (Sachs, JD, 2024). The infographic below shows the current situation for each of the 17 SDGs from Red (Major challenges remain) via Orange and Yellow to Green (SDG achieved). It also indicates the trend for each SDG.

Figure 16: Mexico: Country Dashboard (Sachs JD et al, 2024, p. 306)

SDG Dashboards and Trends

Click on a goal to view more information.

Dashboards: ● SDG achieved ● Challenges remain ● Significant challenges remain ● Major challenges remain ● Information unavailable
 Trends: → On track or maintaining SDG achievement → Moderately improving → Stagnating ↓ Decreasing → Trend information unavailable

Mexico's SDG Dashboard does not show any green or yellow. In most cases the trend is stable or slightly forward. The low point is SDG13 (climate action) and SDG16 (peace, justice and strong institutions). Their

status is "Major challenges remain" and their trend is "Decreasing". It actually no longer matters how the fablab sdg profiles for Mexico turn out. The situation is more or less "all time low" and help has been provided on all fronts.

3.5 Fablabs worldwide

At a global level, the WG first of all is interested in which countries have no, few or many fablabs, preferably related to the number of inhabitants and/or the land area of a country. To this end, it calculated the Fablab Density per country.

Table 1: Fablab Density color scale with numbers of countries

Colour	Description	Number of countries N=249	Number of UN Member States N=193
Red	Country without fablabs	110	66
Orange	Country with fablabs but meets no criteria	82	82
Yellow	Country with fablabs that meets only 1 criterion	23	19
Green	Country with fablabs that meets both criteria	34	26

Figure 17: World: Fablab Density by Country

World: Fablab Density by Country

Legend: red: no fablabs, orange: no criteria met, yellow: one criterion met, green: both criteria met
Criteria: no. of fablabs per mil inhabitants >1.0 and/or no. of fablabs per 10,000 km² area > 1.0

World: fablabs: 2,474; countries: 249; retrieved: 2024-07-12

Sources: fablabs.io; countries: wikipedia/iso-3166; geodata: naturalearth and geonames

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If the fablab network wants to claim that countries benefit from the presence of fablabs, it implicitly has the task to ensure that those fablabs are actually there. The relevance of the network for the outside world

increases if it has a presence in every country. According to the table above, this is not yet the case in 110 (out of 249) countries; If we limit ourselves to only the UN member states, there are still 66 (out of 193). The world map shows that Africa is relatively the least endowed with fablabs; as many as 24 UN Member States there do not have a single fablab. It is also striking that Western Europe has the largest fablab density per country and not the USA, which is the cradle of fablabs.

The following map again shows the world, but now filled with data from the Sustainable Development Report 2024 (Sachs, JD, 2024). The blue color intensity indicates how well the implementation of the SDGs is progressing.

Figure 18: Legend Sustainable development Report 2024

Figure 19: World: SDR24 – Overall SDG Index by Country

World: Sustainable Development Report 2024 - Overall Score by Country

Legend: grey: no data, blue: sequential color map (5 steps)
Color map from light to dark: 0-50%, 50-60%, 60-70%, 70-80%, 80-100%

World: based on Sachs, J.D., Lafortune, G., Fuller, G. (2024); The SDGs and the UN Summit of the Future; Sustainable Development Report 2024; Paris: SDSN, Dublin: Dublin University Press; 10.25546/108572
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The SDG index is high in Western Europe and Scandinavia, medium in North and South America and Low in Africa, the Middle East and Southeast Asia. So countries where help is most needed score the lowest in fablab density. The opposite world?

3.6 Online products

Table 2: Online products by WG Fablabs & SDGs

Name	Number of views (medio 2024)	Source
Fablab Life Cycle report	19,000	Slideshare and Researchgate
Fablab Alignment manual	4,000	Slideshare and Researchgate
Overview of Fablab SDG Profiles	6,000	share.mindmanager.com
Explore the SDGs – all languages	9,000	share.mindmanager.com

4 Conclusion

Figure 20: Maturity levels with interventions

Seven years ago, the Global Working Group Fablabs and UN Sustainable Development Goals was launched. The direction of development was clear; the route by no means. Since then, the group has mapped out that route step-by-step. The result is a growth model based on the maturity levels Awareness, Alignment, Action and Accountability; other organizations also more or less found that path.

The WG has tried from year to year to get the fablabs on board with that route and to support them. Each maturity level requires its own approach. Moreover, the fablabs do not form a cohort that moves at the same time, but each fablab does so at its own pace. The WG should not get too far ahead of the troops. On the contrary, it will have to continue to pay attention to each maturity level because there are fablabs in each of the stages.

Every month, the Working Group produces an updated online overview of Fablab SDG profiles (and much more). The impact of this is greater fablabs visibility, to each other and to the outside world, and thus a stronger fablab network (WG Fablabs & SDGs, 2018 ...).

The spin-off of the working group is the development of a data workbench to manage its own auxiliary administration of SDG profiles, link them to the fablab register and combine them with relevant data from

the outside world, often at country level. Maybe it would be a good idea to add a data workbench to the basic set of fablab machines? (Repository: Workshop Data Workbench)

Awareness and Alignment stages are well on track in terms of methodology and facilitation. Action has an urgent need for more recording and sharing of information. Accountability needs to further crystallize the impact-by-design method. Also for the working group itself!

Acknowledgements

This report is based on the work of the Global Working Group Fablabs and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Portal: Fablabs and SDGs); current members are: Pieter van der Hijden (coordinator) (The Netherlands & Suriname), Enrico Bassi (Italy), Vaneza Caycho Ñuflo (Peru), Nagwa Elnwisy (Egypt), Neville Govender (South Africa), Ted Hung (Taiwan), Arundhati Jadhav (India), Beno Juarez (Peru), Yogesh Kulkarni (India), Noksy Letsoalo (South Africa), Lucía Lucas (Spain), Jean-Baptiste Natali (New Zealand), Mess Wright (USA)

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- Portal: Fablabs.io; Fablab Register; <https://fablabs.io>
- Portal: Labs; Fabwiki; Fablab Iceland; <http://wiki.fablab.is/wiki/Portal:Labs>
- Portal: UNDP Accelerator Labs; <https://www.undp.org/acceleratorlabs>
- Repository: Fablab Network Data; archived fab register; jupyter notebooks for processing; <https://gitlab.fabcloud.org/fl-management/fab-lab-network-data>
- Repository: SDG Workshop; aggregated SDG profiles, SDG texts and logos, alignment workshop kit; <https://gitlab.fabcloud.org/fl-management/fl-sdgs/sdg-workshop>
- Repository: Workshop Data Workbench; introduction to data workbench concept, jupyter notebook, data and fablabs; <https://gitlab.fabcloud.org/fl-management/workshop-data-workbench>
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